

International Conference on Composite Materials
August 4, 2025

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ENERGY ABSORPTION IN OCCUPANT PROTECTION SYSTEMS VIA CELLULAT MATERIALS

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Objective

- *Objective: To dissipate energy in vehicle systems to protect occupants and payloads from repetitive shock, crash and blast loads*
- *Technical Approach: Cellular materials, passive then semi-active*
- *Energy absorption is $EA = \text{Force times displacement}$*
 - *Want a rectangular load stroke profile for high crush efficiency*

Foams and Cellular Solids

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- Foams, aka cellular solids: occupant protection system, electronic packaging, load-bearing structures, thermal insulation, and buoyancy.
- Research areas: Increasing strength, energy absorption, reducing density, decreasing costs, etc.
- Energy absorption via deformation and failure of cellular structures
- Microstructural and material design are critical.

Energy Absorption in Cellular Materials

- In this study, we focus on out-of-plane crushing of cellular materials
- Notional schematic of the stress-strain curve for crushable cellular materials

In the progressive collapse region, cellular materials can absorb impact energy and experience permanent plastic deformations like fracture or cracking of their cells

What is Energy Absorption and Crush Efficiency?

- The blue-shaded area is energy absorbed per unit volume, $U_{EA}(\epsilon)$

$$U_{EA}(\epsilon) = \int_0^{\epsilon} \sigma(\epsilon) d\epsilon$$

- The red box shape is ideal energy absorbed per unit volume, $U_{ideal}(\epsilon)$.

$$U_{ideal}(\epsilon) = \max[\sigma(0), \sigma(\epsilon)] \times \epsilon$$

Here $\max[\cdot]$ selects largest value of a set

- The strain-dependent crush efficiency, $\eta_{SD}(\epsilon)$

$$\eta_{SD}(\epsilon) = \frac{U_{EA}(\epsilon)}{U_{ideal}(\epsilon)} = \frac{\sigma_{mc}(\epsilon)}{\max[\sigma(0), \sigma(\epsilon)]}$$

Energy Absorption Efficiency, $\eta_{EA}(\epsilon)$

$\bar{\eta}_{EA}$: maximum energy absorption efficiency

- Energy absorption efficiency, $\eta_{EA}(\epsilon)$

$$\eta_{EA}(\epsilon) = \frac{U_{EA}(\epsilon)}{U_{ideal f}(\epsilon)} = \frac{\sigma_{mc}(\epsilon) \epsilon}{\max[\sigma(0), \sigma(\epsilon)] \epsilon_f}$$

- Energy absorption efficiency, $\eta_{EA}(\epsilon)$ will have a maximum peak value before the densification and will monotonically decrease after the densification

$$\epsilon_d = \epsilon \quad \text{at} \quad \eta_{EA}(\epsilon) = \bar{\eta}_{EA}$$

ϵ_d : densification strain or effective strain range

Injury and Damage Criteria

Two different application cases of honeycomb structures for the criteria for damage and injuries

- Case (a):
Since $\sigma_{pk} < \sigma_{cr,a}$, it satisfies the criteria, $\sigma_{cr,a}$. But, since the plateau stress is much lower than $\sigma_{cr,a}$, the energy-absorbing performance for $\sigma_{cr,a}$ is low.
- Case (b):
Since $\sigma_{pk} > \sigma_{cr,b}$, it fails to satisfy the criteria, $\sigma_{cr,b}$. But, since the plateau stress is close to $\sigma_{cr,b}$, the energy-absorbing performance for $\sigma_{cr,b}$ is high.

Motivation and Background (5)

Honeycombs without buckling initiators

- $\sigma_{pk} \gg \sigma_{pl}$
- **Crush efficiency, $\eta_{SD}(\varepsilon) \ll 1$: Low**
- **Crashworthiness: It fails to meet the criteria for the damage or injuries while maintaining good crush efficiency**

Honeycombs with buckling initiators

- $\sigma_{pk} \approx \sigma_{pl}$
- **Crush efficiency, $\eta_{SD}(\varepsilon) \approx 1$: High**
- **Crashworthiness: It meets the criteria for the damage or injuries while maintaining good crush efficiency**

Outline

- Passive energy absorption and additive manufacturing (AM)
 - Glass Foams
 - ABS Honeycomb cellular materials with buckling initiators
 - TPU Honeycomb cellular materials with buckling initiators
 - Conclusions

Amorphous glass foam

- The key figure of merit: maximum energy absorption at minimum density.
- Specific energy absorption (U)

$$U \propto \frac{\sigma_S}{\rho_S} \varepsilon_D,$$

σ_S : Failure stress of the bulk solid

ρ_S : Density of the bulk solid

ε_D : Densification strain

$\frac{\sigma_S}{\rho_S}$: Specific strength

Materials	Failure stress (MPa)	Density (kg/m ³)	Specific strength (MJ/kg)
Soda lime borosilicate (3M iM16)	774	2230	0.333
2800 Maraging steel	2693	8000	0.337
Zr based BMG	1723	6100	0.282
Titanium 11	1040	4500	0.231
2014-T6 aluminum alloy	483	2800	0.173

Glass foam fabrication

Hollow glass spheres

Packing process

Sintering process

Uniaxial compression testing

Glass foam

Large glass foam

3D printable (dry powder printing)

Machinable

3D printable (wet powder printing)

Process optimization

Sintering process optimization is critical to achieving large energy absorption while keeping the density of foams low.

Characterization

Microstructure shows good consolidation and MTS test shows the highest energy absorption around 830-840C. other processing parameters such as ramp rate, cooling rate, and annealing temperature (to remove residual stress)

Tailorable Energy Absorption

passenger undergoes large impact stress.

A functionally graded foam can utilize a density gradient to improve the energy-absorbing capacity over a wider range of stress levels. The stress wave profile and amplitude can be tailored by the gradient function (density gradient), which improves the energy absorption capacity and reduces the damage probability of damage or injury.

Tailorable EA glass foam

Two types of hollow glass spheres with different densities were used to form a bilayer structure by employing a co-sintering process.

The bilayer foams are sintered at the same time, so the density change at the interface is not abrupt. (Typically, epoxy is used in the interface)

Fabrication

(a) Bilayer foam by co-sintering

Fabricating bilayers with different thickness ratios between the layers achieve a tunable stress-strain profile.

Fabrication is challenging since accurate control of layer thickness as well as a uniform interface between the layers is required.

(b)

Dry powder printing (DPP)

Printing rate of 0.2 g/min

The density of the 9 foams printed is 0.37 ± 0.01 g/cc, indicating that the DPP system prints samples in a reproducible manner.

Characterization

	a	b	c	d	e
Thickness ratio K20/K46	Uniform K46	1:3	1:1	3:1	Uniform K20
Density (g/cc)	0.36 ± 0.00	0.32 ± 0.00	0.27 ± 0.00	0.22 ± 0.00	0.18 ± 0.00
Energy absorption (kJ/kg)	3.04 ± 0.15	2.45 ± 0.07	2.30 ± 0.12	1.93 ± 0.10	1.51 ± 0.13

Co-sintered vs. Epoxy-bonded

Epoxy-bonded bilayer (S32 and K46)

Co-sintered bilayer (S32 and K46)

S32 density: 0.43 g/cc
K46 density: 0.37 g/cc

The interfacial effect is not prominent.

Summary: Glass Foams

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- High-strength and low-density glass foam via sintering hollow glass microspheres
- Sintering process was optimized by controlling sintering temperature and soaking time to achieve a glass foam with a high specific strength.
- Density graded glass foam with tailorable stress-strain profile can be fabricated using dry powder printing.
 - Using different densities in different layers
 - Smoothen modulus between first and second plateau stresses
 - Establishing predictable energy absorption
- Glass foam can limit impact stress on an occupant and perform effective energy absorption to minimize injury
- Design multilayer foam to allow finer tunability and a gradual increase in stress to be achieved for diverse impact conditions.

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Objectives

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Seek to reduce peak stresses of honeycomb samples without reducing their plateau stresses

- Buckling initiators (BIs) introduced at top of the honeycomb walls at vertices
- BIs can significantly alleviate the undesirable high peak collapse stress to increase energy absorption efficiency
- Honeycomb samples made via additive manufacturing (FFF): ABS plastic filament material
- Quasi-steady stress vs. strain is measured
- The effects of BI size (0, 1, 2, 3 mm hole) at the top of the honeycomb cell are measured

Honeycombs with BIs

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No BI Case

$D=15\text{ mm}$
 $t=0.8\text{ mm}$
 $h=35\text{ mm}$

- BI diameters
1 mm, 2 mm,
3 mm
- BI locations
Top of HC

BI Case

Experimental Tests (1)

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- An MTS machine was used.
- The top platen was fixed and connected to the load cell.
- The tested samples were compressed as the bottom platen moved upward to an 85% strain with a constant speed of 0.05 mm/s.
- The displacement of the bottom platen was measured using a LVDT sensor.

Crushed Honeycomb Samples

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■ Photograph of the honeycomb sample after the compression tests

No BI case

BI case (3 mm, 0h)

- Both cases could neatly form the progressive folding wave until the maximum strain tested in this study.
- The ABS plastic used in this study was stiff, but also sufficiently ductile rather than brittle.

Typical Stress vs. Strain (Quasi-static)

- Buckling initiators showed a smooth transient from the initial peak stress to the plateau stress
- BI size has impact on reducing the peak stress

Quasi-static Crush of No BI Samples

- Observe panel buckling
- HC starts crushing at bottom
- Also panel buckling
- Too strong and a high peak stress

Quasi-static Crush of BI Samples

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- Observe no panel buckling
- HC starts crushing at bottom
- Peak stress reduced

Strain=0

Strain=0.05

Strain=0.1

Strain=0.15

Strain=0.2

Strain=0.25

Strain=0.3

Strain=0.4

Strain=0.5

Strain=0.6

Strain=0.7

Strain=0.85

Measuring Energy Absorption

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Strain-dependent crush efficiency, $\eta_{SD}(\epsilon)$

Energy absorption efficiency, $\eta_{EA}(\epsilon)$

- The energy absorption efficiency, $\eta_{EA}(\epsilon)$, indicates how much the energy absorbed at a certain strain is close to the ideal energy absorbed when honeycomb structures are fully compressed with their peak stresses.
- Strain-dependent crush efficiency, $\eta_{SD}(\epsilon)$, indicates how much the energy absorbed at a certain strain is close to the ideal energy absorbed over that strain range

Peak stress versus the mean crush stress

mean crush stress: $\sigma_{mc}(\epsilon = \epsilon_d)$

peak stress: $\max[\sigma(0), \sigma(\epsilon = \epsilon_d)]$

- The red-colored diagonal line signifies the ideal strain-dependent crush efficiency, $\eta_{SD,ideal}$

$$\eta_{SD,ideal} = \frac{\sigma_{mc}(\epsilon_d)}{\max[\sigma(0), \sigma(\epsilon_d)]} = 1$$

- The green-colored area above the ideal diagonal line is the physically infeasible mean crush stress area.
- The vertical distance between the ideal diagonal line and each data graphically indicates the stress difference between the mean crush stress and the peak stress.
- BI of 3mm diameter at top of sample were best

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Viscoelastic Honeycomb Samples

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- Examine TPU honeycomb samples with BIs and no BIs
 - Do we see similar benefits when adding BIs?
 - Soft elastomeric materials are a little harder to 3D print (FFF)
 - Modified extruders to handle soft elastomers
 - Place diamond BIs at vertices at half height
- Quasi-static crush
- Dynamic Crush!!

Stress vs. Strain for TPU Honeycomb Samples

No Buckling Initiators

Buckling Initiators

Panel buckling (0BI) vs. Folding (1BI)

- No BI case exhibits panel buckling as for ABS-R samples
- 1BI case exhibits folding as for ABS-R samples
- Folding produces greater crush efficiency

Crush Efficiency of TPU HC

- Folding induced by BIs produces greater crush efficiency

Computational Verification

- Use ABAQUS
- Not simple, but can be done
- Crush is a highly nonlinear computational problem

New CORE Lab Capability

← CADEX drop stand or helmet tester is 16 ft tall and drops a 5 kg mass

Close-up of hemispherical impactor (top) and flat anvil on the bottom →

Drop Testing Using CADEX

4 m/s or 9 mph (14.5 km/hr)

- No BI
- Recovers shape after impact

- BI
- Recovers shape after impact

Velocity and Displacement

Energy absorption – V_0 Varies

- High peak stress
- Lower strain range per ΔV

- Peak stress closer to mean stress
- Strain strain range per ΔV
- Take this one!

Conclusions

- Cellular materials provide energy absorbing materials
 - Introduce geometric features (BIs) to encourage folding and increase crush efficiency
 - Tailor energy absorption to specific situations and payloads
- Energy absorption can be tailored using
 - Density gradients (glass foams)
 - Buckling initiators (honeycombs)
- Additive Manufacturing makes this feasible
 - Conventional processes can't make the designs we come up with

Future Work: Electroplated Structures

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Ferromagnetic Honeycombs!
Cheaper than metal AM!

Initial results: Quasi-static Crush

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UNPLATED – brittle fracture, EA bad

PLATED – Crush, Energy absorption has potential for application

Future Work: Tubulane Structures

Tubulane Structures – similar structures to cancellous bone. Each sample has the same volume of brittle plastic material. The 2x2x2 thru 4x4x4 samples break and shatter. The 5x5x5 samples crushes, indicated a strong dependence on geometry.

SAMPE Journal – send papers!

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Society for the Advancement of Material Process Engineering (SAMPE) Journal

Acknowledgement

- US Navy SBIR program
- UMD Fellowships

U N I V E R S I T Y O F M A R Y L A N D

Thank you!

Questions?